

RACIALIZED GOVERNMENTALITY: MAPPING THE PERSISTENCE OF ISLAMOPHOBIA IN THE WEST

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Islamophobia; racialized
governmentality; far-right
discourses; social media
algorithms; digital Islamophobia

Article History

Received: 20 June 2025

Accepted: 30 August 2025

Published: 11 September 2025

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Abstract

Islamophobia has become more than a historical prejudice; it is complex and intricate mechanism of marginalisation in the 21st-century West. This paper suggests that contemporary Islamophobia is most productively approached not as 'phobia', or simple prejudice, but as a kind of racialized governmentality which functions (a) at the level of the state and policy (b) in rhetoric and political speech and (c) in societal practice. Rather than offering simply a historical perspective, the analysis integrates the genesis of Islamophobia with its contemporary implications. Drawing on case studies from the UK, US, Canada and Australia, this article thematically deconstructs threefold main drivers of contemporary Islamophobia: 1) state-led securitization and surveillance; 2) political assimilation of far-right discourses; and 3) gendered, digital forms of social hostility. Combining the emerging picture with post-2020 trends - including changes wrought by social media algorithms and new anti-Muslim legislation - the paper reveals a deep-rooted, technologically sophisticated Islamophobia that continues to serve as an obstinate threat to the fundamental principles of liberal democracies in the West.

INTRODUCTION

The post-2020 period has seen great strides in Islamophobia discourse, with the controversy around France's "anti-separatism" law (which both seeks to govern Muslim practices under the pretext of national security) serving as a case in point. There has been much debate over the degree (Nasir, 2025) to which the state encroaches upon individual freedoms, the relationship between it and Islamophobia, and the rapid escalation of anti-Muslim rhetoric that permeates Western societies. An upsurge in hate crimes against Muslims has been

reported, bringing an added layer of complexity to the socio-political landscape and a pressing need for insightful analysis of the fast-changing scenario (Tama & Sulistyaningrum, 2023; Tariq & Iqbal, 2023).

This article proposes that contemporary Islamophobia constitutes a racialized governmentality, demonstrating through relations between the state, political, and socio-digital mechanism. Recent literature has argued that Islamophobia is not the product of individual

prejudices, but is ingrained in institutional practices and (political) discourses (Mekki-Berrada & d'Haenens, 2023; Raemdonck, 2023). Such a reading is consistent with evidence from multiple studies that indicate how state laws have been wielded to legitimize discriminatory acts against Muslims in public (Zuhri, 2021).

To begin with, the paper will theorize Islamophobia as an integral component of systemic racism, which makes it a complex phenomenon and one that is deeply connected to historical precedence. This background, encompassing a number of events from the advent of right-populism to substantial international events such as the Christchurch Call, will be described to demonstrate how such incidents have inflamed Islamophobia (Ali, 2021). The thematic analysis will track three interrelated underpinnings of contemporary Islamophobia: state sanctioned securitization and surveillance, the political normalization of the far-right discourse, and the gendered and digital modes of social hostility (Raemdonck, 2023; Lubis et al., 2023). Lastly, implications of these findings will be discussed with a reflection on the ways in which Islamophobia remains an entrenched challenge to the liberalism and democracy in established Western states.

2. Conceptualizing Islamophobia: From a Contested Term to a Theory of Racialization

Islamophobia, defined in the academic literature from the 1990s, comprises a nexus of predispositions, systemic prejudices and socio-political interactions aimed at Muslims. The 1997 report by the Runnymede Trust led the way with its defining comment: "Islamophobia is a form of racism, as is anti-Semitism", adding that it "targets expressions of Muslimness or perceived Muslimness" (Sufi & Yasmin, 2022). This definition was highly controversial with respect to its implications, especially the inclusion of the term "phobia". Critics claimed that to label Islamophobia a "phobia" is to assert a kind of irrationality that neglects how systemic and structural issues are the foundation for anti-Muslim discrimination. Rather, some argue in favour of framing this as a form of racism, embedded in socio-political and cultural contexts (Vyas et al., 2021).

The attacks in 2001 marked a turning point where the discourse around hostility toward Islam perpetuated a shift from "unfounded hostility" to one that is "ingrained in the fabric of society." In the wake of 9/11 Muslims were identified with terrorism in many public discourses, which resulted in rampant discrimination and violence (Hafez, 2020). Within this framework, the first crucial move was made towards the understanding of Islamophobia not simply as religious bigotry rather a 'complex form of racism', a process facilitated by the work of academics like S. Sayyid, who in 2014 coined the term "racialized governmentality" (Razamin et al., 2023). Sayyid contended that the racialization of Muslims is based on extrinsic markers of Muslimness—be it clothing, names or perceived piousness—and not ethnicity or nationality per se. This concept recasts Islamophobia within discussions of state power, surveillance, and social exclusion, providing insight into the fact that anti-Muslim hatred as a construct of history and society rather than an innate revulsion.

In the most recent categorization of what constitutes Islamophobia, based on the 2017 Runnymede report, The scope of the definition for islamophobia was widened to explicitly categorise it as "anti-Muslim Racism" (Sufi & Yasmin, 2022). This process suggests a broader consensus emerging within academia and policy-making circles on conceptualising Islamophobia as a racialized ideology that exists within the fabric of society, rather than simply as individual prejudices, and specifically throughout society in those institutions from which Muslims experience systemic forms of oppression in everyday life. This growing awareness is critical in shaping discussions about policy responses and community initiatives to challenge Islamophobia.

Furthermore, the gendered aspects of Islamophobia have lately been focused in the recent research. Research has demonstrated that Muslim women, especially those with headscarves (hijabs and niqabs), are the most affected by disparate treatment and hostility (Alimahomed-Wilson, 2020). Iman Atta's work with Tell MAMA (Measuring Anti-Muslim Abuse) has highlighted the intersectionality of gender and religious hatred and has highlighted that Muslim women's experiences have revealed a multi-dimensionality within anti-Muslim narratives (Wang

et al., 2020). Women whose Muslimness is visible encounter increased surveillance and violence—and so, Islamophobia is not uniform across gender lines. This gendered nature permeates public policy as well; indeed, attempts to define Islamophobia have faced political opposition in a current climate, for example, in the UK, where the controversies over the definition proposed by the All-Party Parliamentary Group (APPG) suggest arguments about the recognition of Islamophobia as a unique form of racial discrimination (Vyas et al., 2021). The opposition reflects fears that an official definition could restrict free speech, or be used to suppress legitimate political discourse.

As we grapple with the complexities of Islamophobia, important work on the subject by scholars such as Peter Hopkins and Tahir Abbas highlight the diversity of Islamophobia in Western settings, encompassing mainstream media representations to the development of far-right narratives that victimise Muslims (Jurekovič, 2024). Their observations underscore the requirement to tackle Islamophobia as a whole, as an integration of individual biases and institutional discrimination and state-endorsed measures that sideline Muslim communities.

Indeed, for current manifestations of Islamophobia we also have in depth reports such as that from The Bridge Initiative and from the Council on American-Islamic Relations (CAIR). Their findings correspond to the warnings issued by scholars in relation to the desensitization to anti-Muslim rhetoric as well as the increasing tolerance of discriminatory language in the public sphere (Razamin et al., 2023; Peucker, 2021). The reciprocation between rhetoric and reality reflects the urgency of undertaking research and advocacy that give agency to historically subordinated groups in challenging underlying social, political, and economic disparities that animate Islamophobia.

In conclusion, the definition of Islamophobia has come a long way from its early definitions toward a more complex understanding that also includes systemic racism, gendered dynamics, and intersectional advocacy. Framing Islamophobia as a racial phenomenon also creates a platform for improved public policy responses and social change. Understanding these complexities is vital if we want

to work for an equitable and inclusive society at a time when Islamophobic undertones are worsening.

3. The Contemporary Architecture of Islamophobia: A Thematic Analysis

Given that Islamophobia is expressed across the complex mosaic of the Western world, our thematic analysis is necessarily multifaceted in order to be able to grasp its dimensions in the present society. The section concentrates on three central themes that encase the architecture of Islamophobia, which are; the securitised state, mainstreaming of the far-right and Islamophobia industry and also, the socio-cultural aversion towards Muslim communities. Every theme draws on the UK, USA, Australia and Canada to demonstrate worldwide patterns of anti-Muslim sentiment.

3.1. The Securitized State: Counter-Terrorism, Surveillance, and Immigration

Islamophobia has been steadily becoming an institutional policy for western powers under the mantra of anti-terrorism laws and security measures that, in most of these cases, are against Muslim populations. Such a notion of the "suspect community" captures the way Muslim identities have been inextricably folded into suspicion and regulatory surveillance. Policing strategies appear in major initiatives such as the UK Prevent strategy, UK Terrorism Acts, US PATRIOT Act, Australian counter-terror laws, and Canadian Anti-Terrorism Act. These policies facilitate racialized surveillance of Muslims in communal spaces, including mosques, cultural centers, and humanitarian charities, which is said to have a chilling effect on civilian rights (Lajevardi et al. 2023; Mekki-Berrada & d'Haenens, 2023; Riaz, 2023).

This landscape is further complicated by the rapid expansion of digital surveillance. Algorithms are used by governments to spy on online spaces, where "extremist" material is searched for, casting a pursuit of suspicion over mainstream Islamic discourse. It is not just social media platforms that are engaged in this monitoring, with multiple governments directly tracking (potentially dangerous) on-line behaviors against loosely defined categories of extremism (Afzal et al., 2021; Alimahomed-Wilson, 2020). The ramifications of this (re-)affirmation of stories about

radicalization effectively impede a number of Islamic expressions from being heard in digital media, is something that is being brought to the fore in the work of Arun Kundnani, who debunks mythmaking around radicalization as an alibi for additional stigmatization (Mekki-Berrada & d'Haenens, 2023). Recent immigration provisions emphasize this narrative of securitization. The "Muslim Ban" in the United States is testament to this, displaying the brazen simultaneous collusion of national security and anti-Muslimism. This exclusionary policy "raises disturbing questions about the systemic racism toward Muslim refugees and migrants fleeing conflict and seeking shelter in countries like Syria and Afghanistan" (Alimahomed-Wilson, 2020; Hodson, 2020). Canada has had similar discussions concerning refugees, where skepticism about Muslim identities persists (Alimahomed-Wilson 2020). Thus, these trends feed into a larger narrative in which Muslims are constantly framed as suspects and criminalized in public discourse as the "other"—a historical framework necessary for understanding the contribution of government policies that justify Islamic profiling and limiting civil liberties.

3.2. Political and Civil Society: The Mainstreaming of the Far-Right and the Islamophobia Industry

Islamophobic discourse has been breaking into the political mainstream in a number of Western countries rapidly, from the fringes to the core of political discussion. That is due in part to the rise of what is commonly known as the "Islamophobia industry," a network of think tanks, activists and journalists who are peddling anti-Muslim rhetoric. Prominent personalities such as Robert Spencer and Pamela Geller, meanwhile, have worked side by side with conventional conservative politicians, translating their ideology into possible political speech (Panighel, 2023; Abbas, 2020).

The emphasis on fabricated "crises" surrounding Sharia law, halal food practices, and the right to establish mosques enable the mobilizing of a political base ingrained in terror and distrust. These techniques have helped shape public opinion as far-right groups such as the English Defence League (EDL), Reclaim Australia and PEGIDA Canada have further capitalized on these narratives to push their political agendas. Such is the case with Islamophobic

discourse across borders, the techniques deployed in the United States mirror those used in Europe, Canada, and Australia as part of an international enterprise to establish anti-Muslim sentiment as a hallmark of nationalist rhetoric. Farid Hafez's findings demonstrate how these discourses work in policy-making and public opinion across borders and with frightening continuity (Cervi, 2020; Bukar, 2020).

Gradually this political climate has led to serious consideration of fear and misrepresentations as instruments of socio-political manipulation. Positioning Islamophobia as a successful tool of control, there is a way in which anti-Muslim politics can be examined as emerging from broader forms of power that rely on creating a binary between 'us' and 'them', preventing connection and collaboration for different communities.

3.3. Socio-Cultural Hostility: Gendered Attacks, Media Tropes, and the Digital Frontier

Islamophobia has substantial social and cultural impact which is reflected in both everyday street-level hate crimes, negative media portrayals and persecution of Muslims in online spaces. This social animosity infiltrates community activities, where experiences of Islamophobia are causing Muslims to disengage from grassroots football in England and Wales (Awan & Zempi, 2025). Similarly, gendered aggression in the form of verbal intimidation, pulling off headscarves and attacks on the women wearing the veil are some examples of gendered attacks Muslims encounter (Gatta, 2023; Mekki-Berrada & d'Haenens, 2023). Legislation that sought to control Muslim dress, for instance, Bill 21 in Quebec prohibiting religious symbols in the public places, mirrors the political antipathy towards visible demonstrations of faith that fuel Islamophobic atmospheres (Abubakar et al., 2022).

Media portrayals are a key factor in the propagation of negative stereotypes about Muslims, who are frequently represented as violent fanatics or extremists. This media canvas has been more intense in representations around ISIS or the return of the Taliban, affecting dominant views and attitudes towards Muslims (Riaz, 2023). Popular culture equally contributes to this phenomenon by rarely presenting alternative narratives that show the varied

aspects and richness of Muslim life. Rather, contemporary representations further confirm the status of Muslims as eternal aliens (Steenburg, 2020; Sengul, 2022).

The use of media narratives as a weapon against Muslims is nothing new. For decades Western press has been filled with evidence of consistent portrayals of the Muslim world in a negative light. Scholarly examinations have revealed that media stories consistently represent Islam as monolithic and inherently associated with violence, facilitating the normalization of anti-Muslim sentiment. Siraj (2012) examines the historical trajectory to Islamophobia in Western journalism with its tendency to view Muslims through a hostile, pejorative lens. Baugut and Neumann (2019) also observe that negative depictions by the media deepen the cognitive radicalization of Muslims, pinpointing the damaging effects of stereotypical images of Islam. These stock media tropes, in which Muslims are still frequently portrayed as menacing outsiders or as a monolithic retrograde block, have provided fertile ground for the more virulent and more rapidly proliferating varieties of digital Islamophobia now rampant on the internet. Awan (2022) investigates these digital incarnations further, to illustrate how online spaces reinforce and amplify anti-Muslim prejudice.

Furthermore, negative illustration of Islam is not restricted to Western media; even within Muslim-majority nations, media misrepresentation may contribute to Islamophobia, thus suggesting a global trend (Hassan & Azmi, 2021). This argument is in line with the conclusions reached by Hassan et al., (2020) who suggest that the portrayal of Islam in the news constructs the idea that Islam is a threat to Western values. Combined, these studies highlight the negative effects of media framing on Muslims' representations in the public and the urgency for a more informed and responsible media depiction in traditional and online media settings.

Islamophobia in its digital manifestation is the new threat as its hate campaigns and disinformation are organized through social media. Facebook, Twitter/X, and TikTok are used to disseminate Islamophobia, with online abuse specifically targeting Muslim women who experience unique kinds of abuse because of their outward expressions of their faith (Baker et al., 2020). The Christchurch Call is an

international pledge that aims to counter online extremism and covertly exhibited terrorism-related content, demonstrating an awareness of the necessity to address the problem (Öztiğ et al., 2020).

Recent reports by groups such as Tell MAMA (UK), FBI (US) and Statistics Canada have recorded surges in anti-Muslim hate crime in connection with political events such as terrorist attacks or the application of extreme anti-Muslimism rhetoric by public figures (Riaz, 2023; Imam et al., 2023). The results reveal a distressing relationship between political levels of Islamophobia and street level violence on Muslims, which only perpetuates the hate that Muslim communities face.

In other words, the architecture of Islamophobia today works along several interlinked dimensions. From state-sponsored discrimination within institutions to broad acceptance of discrimination within civil society and the media, these also contribute to the reinforcement of Muslims' marginalization. It is important for us to grapple with such complex dynamics in order to dismantle such systems that perpetuate Islamophobia and challenge them to construct a more inclusive society.

4. Conclusion

To conclude, Islamophobia cannot be easily relegated to the status of irrational prejudice, but well-entrenched civilizational and racialized exclusion, immanent to state institutions, political debate, and cultural practices. This structure elucidates how institutional policies, and exclusively counter-terrorist security measures, have produced an environment in which Muslims are subject to undue surveillance (i.e., monitoring) and exclusion (i.e., separation). These dynamics of state security and mainstream political processing of anti-Muslim distress, in conjunction with socio-digital hostility, amount to a full-fledged structure of Islamophobia, which both sustains the alienation and exclusion of Muslim communities.

Islamophobia and its perseverance and its continued transformation pose substantial risks for Western nations. Such a culture not only erodes democratic norms, but also subverts social solidarity, enabling not just the normalization of racism against Muslims, but all minorities. While the tide of polarization rises in society, Islamophobia could have spill-over effects

in other segments where diversity and community harmony and engagement are actively pursued.

In efforts to disentangle these problems in a meaningful way, there are several lines of future study. Comparative research into the effectiveness of different state approaches to online hate, might contribute to best practices when it comes to addressing digital Islamophobia. Furthermore, such qualitative ethnographic investigation will shed light on how Muslim youth mitigate their identities under the gaze of digital monitoring and surveillance, and the intricacies that newer generations face in this regard. Finally, examining instances of effective counter-narratives, and the examples of grassroots pushback against the Islamophobia industry, may offer avenues to strengthen and build resilience in response to systemic forms of exclusion. These are the key research pathways necessary to progress towards a society that respects and appreciate diversity, equity and social justice.

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